

**DETERMINANTLAR NAZARIYASINI ANALITIK
GEOMETRIYA MASALALARIGA TADBIQI**

¹Berdiyorov Azamat

Oliy matematika kafedrası dotsenti

e-mail: berdiyorov57@gmail.com,

²Arslanov Dostonbek

Talaba, Jizzax politexnika institute.

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ABSTRACT

Ko'rilayotgan maqolada chiziqli algebra elementlaridan ya'ni ikkinchi va uchinchi tartibli determinantni hisoblash formulasidan foydalanib analitik geometriya masalalaridan bir nechta namunalar ko'rib chiqilgan.

Determinantlar bizga elementar algebradan ma'lum bo'lgan permutatsiya (o'rin almashtirishlar) bilan bog'liqdir. Istalgan n ta musbat butun sonni, masalan 1 dan n gacha bo'lgan 1, 2, 3, 4.... n sonlarni olamiz. Bu sonlardan hammasi bo'lib

$$n! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot \dots \cdot n$$

ta har xil permutatsiya (o'rin almashtirishlar) tuzish mumkin. Masalan, 1, 2, 3 sonlardan hammasi bo'lib,

$$3! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 = 6$$

ta har xil permutatsiya tuzamiz: 123, 132, 213, 231, 312, 321.

Ta'rif: n -tartibli determinant deb, $n!$ hadlardan tuzilgan algebraik yig'indiga aytiladi. Bunda yig'indining har bir hadi determinantdagi n ta elementning ko'paytmasidan iborat. Agar hadlarning hammasida elementlarning birinchi n raqamlari tartib bilan (ya'ni 1, 2, 3... n) yozilsa, ikkinchi raqamlari 1, 2, 3... n raqamlardan tuziladigan $n!$ ta permutatsiya tashkil etadi. Analitik geometriya masalalarini yechishda quyidagi

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{vmatrix} = ad - cb$$

ikkinchi tartibli determinant va

$$\begin{vmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & c_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 & c_2 \\ a_3 & b_3 & c_3 \end{vmatrix} = a_1b_2c_3 + b_1c_2a_3 + c_1a_2b_3 - c_1b_2a_3 - b_1a_2c_3 - a_1c_2b_3$$

uchinchi tartibli determinantni hisoblash formulalaridan foydalanamiz.

Bu formulalar yordamida bir nechta masalalarni ko'rib chiqamiz.

1-masala: A(-3;8) va B(5;-1) nuqtalar orqali o'tuvchi to'g'ri chiziq tenglamasini tuzing hamda shu to'g'ri chiziqda absissiyasi 1 ga teng bo'lgan nuqtani toping.

Yechish: Ikki nuqta orqali o'tuvchi to'g'ri chiziq tenglamasini quyidagi formulalar orqali topamiz.

$$\begin{vmatrix} x & y & 1 \\ x_1 & y_1 & 1 \\ x_2 & y_2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

Demak

$$\begin{vmatrix} x & y & 1 \\ -3 & 8 & 1 \\ 5 & -1 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

$$8x + 5y + 3 - 40 + 3y + x = 0$$

Ixchamlasak,

$$9x + 8y - 37 = 0$$

bo'ladi.

Bu to'g'ri chiziqda absissasi 1 ga teng bo'lgan nuqtani koordinatasini topish uchun uch nuqtani bir to'g'ri chiziqda yotish shartidan foydalanamiz. Ya'ni,

$$\begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 1 \\ x_2 & y_2 & 1 \\ x_3 & y_3 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

U holda,

$$\begin{vmatrix} -3 & 8 & 1 \\ 5 & -1 & 1 \\ 1 & y & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

$$3 + 8 + 5y + 1 - 40 + 3y = 0 \quad \text{yoki} \quad 8y - 28 = 0 \quad y = 3.5$$

bo'ladi.

Demak, $9x + 8y - 37 = 0$ to'g'ri chiziqda absissasi 1 ga teng bo'lgan nuqta $C(1;3.5)$ bo'ladi. (1-rasm.)

1-rasm.

2-masala. Koordinatalar boshidan to'g'ri chiziqqa tushirilgan OP perpendikular OX o'qi bilan

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{6}$$

burchak hosil qiladi. Agar perpendikular uzunligi 3 bo'lsa, to'g'ri chiziqning normal tenglamasini tuzing.

Yechish: To'g'ri chiziqning normal tenglamasini tuzish uchun quyidagi formuladan foydalanamiz:

$$\begin{vmatrix} x & -\sin \alpha \\ y & \cos \alpha \end{vmatrix} = p$$

Ya'ni,

$$\begin{vmatrix} x & -\sin \frac{\pi}{6} \\ y & \cos \frac{\pi}{6} \end{vmatrix} = 3 \quad \text{yoki} \quad \begin{vmatrix} x & -\frac{1}{2} \\ y & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{vmatrix} = 3$$

bu ikkinchi tartibli determinantni hisoblab, $\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}x + \frac{1}{2}y = 3$ yoki $\sqrt{3}x + y - 6 = 0$ tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz.

3-masala: Uchlari A(2;3), B(4; -1) va C(6;5) bo'lgan uchburchak yuzini hisoblang. (2-rasm.)

2-rasm.

Yechish: Uchburchakning yuzini hisoblash uchun

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \text{mod} \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 1 \\ x_2 & y_2 & 1 \\ x_3 & y_3 & 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

formuladan foydalanib, quyidagicha hisoblashlarni amalga oshiramiz:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \text{mod} \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 3 & 1 \\ 4 & -1 & 1 \\ 6 & 5 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \text{mod} (-2 + 18 + 20 + 6 - 12 - 10) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 20 = 10 \text{ kv.birlik}$$

4-masala: $M_1(3;-1;2)$, $M_2(4;-1;-1)$, $M_3(2;0;2)$ nuqtalardan o'tuvchi tekislik tenglamasini tuzing.

Yechish: Berilgan uchta nuqtadan o'tuvchi tekislik tenglamasini tuzish uchun

$$\begin{vmatrix} x - x_1 & y - y_1 & z - z_1 \\ x_2 - x_1 & y_2 - y_1 & z_2 - z_1 \\ x_3 - x_1 & y_3 - y_1 & z_3 - z_1 \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

formuladan foydalanamiz. U holda

$$\begin{vmatrix} x-3 & y+1 & z-2 \\ 4-3 & -1+1 & -1-2 \\ 2-3 & 0+1 & 2-2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad \text{yoki} \quad \begin{vmatrix} x-3 & y+1 & z-2 \\ 1 & 0 & -3 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

Bundan $0+3(y+1)+z-2-0+0+3(x-3)=0$ yoki $3x+3y+z-8=0$ tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz.

5-masala. Uchlari $A(1;2;3)$, $B(-2;4;1)$, $C(7;6;3)$ va $D(4; -3; -1)$ nuqtalarda bo'lgan piramida berilgan. a) ABC yog'ining yuzi; b) Piramidaning hajmini toping.

3-rasm.

Yechish: a) ABC yog'ining yuzi \overline{AB} va \overline{AC} vektorlarning vektor ko'paytmasi modulini yarmiga teng, ya'ni

$$S_{ABC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot |\overline{AB} \cdot \overline{AC}| = \begin{vmatrix} \vec{i} & \vec{j} & \vec{k} \\ x_1 & y_1 & z_1 \\ x_2 & y_2 & z_2 \end{vmatrix}$$

formula orqali topiladi.

$$\overline{AB} = \{-3; 2; -2\} = -3i + 2j - 2k$$

$$\overline{AC} = \{6; 4; 0\} = 6i + 4j + 0k$$

$$|\overline{AB} \cdot \overline{AC}| = \begin{vmatrix} \vec{i} & \vec{j} & \vec{k} \\ -3 & 2 & -2 \\ 6 & 4 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = -12\vec{j} - 12\vec{k} - 12\vec{k} + 8\vec{i} = 8\vec{i} - 12\vec{j} - 24\vec{k}$$

Demak

$$S_{ABC} = \frac{1}{2} |\overline{AB} \cdot \overline{AC}| = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{8^2 + (-12)^2 + (-24)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{64 + 144 + 576} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{784} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 28 = 14 \quad \text{kv.birlik}$$

b) Piramidaning hajmini topish uchun uch vektorning aralash ko'paytmasidan foydalanamiz. Ya'ni,

$$V_{pir} = \frac{1}{6} \text{mod} \begin{vmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & z_1 \\ x_2 & y_2 & z_2 \\ x_3 & y_3 & z_3 \end{vmatrix}$$

formula yordamida topamiz.

$$\overrightarrow{AB} = -3\vec{i} + 2\vec{j} - 2\vec{k}$$

$$\overrightarrow{AC} = 6\vec{i} + 4\vec{j} + 0\vec{k}$$

$$\overrightarrow{AD} = 3\vec{i} - 5\vec{j} - 4\vec{k}$$

Ekanligini hisobga olsak, V_{pir} ko'rinishi

$$V_{pir} = \frac{1}{6} \bmod \begin{vmatrix} -3 & 2 & -2 \\ 6 & 4 & 0 \\ 3 & -5 & -4 \end{vmatrix} = \frac{1}{6} \bmod (48 + 60 + 24 + 48) = \frac{1}{6} \bmod (180) = 30$$

kub birlik

ga ega bo'lamiz. Demak piramida hajmi 30 kub birlikka teng ekan.

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